

Exploring Vietnamese EFL Lecturers' Attitudes towards AI Integration: Pedagogical Adaptations, Ethical Concerns, and Teaching Philosophies

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INTRODUCTION

The rise of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools such as ChatGPT, Gemini and Copilot has generated both enthusiasm and concern within the field of English as a Foreign Language (EFL). These tools offer the potential to support learning through instant feedback, content generation, and personalised language practice. However, they also raise critical questions about academic integrity, evolving teacher roles, and increasing student dependency (Ngo et al., 2024; Pham & Le, 2024).

In Vietnam, where English Language Teaching (ELT) is considered a national priority, university lecturers increasingly encounter AI in their professional lives, often without clear institutional policies or adequate professional development. While some educators view AI as a threat to traditional pedagogical values, others see it as an opportunity to enhance creativity, learner autonomy, and instructional efficiency (Pham & Le, 2024; Saliba, 2024). Nonetheless, persistent concerns remain regarding plagiarism, student disengagement, and the ethical use of AI tools (Ngo et al., 2024).

International studies have shown that teacher responses to AI vary depending on factors such as digital literacy, institutional support, and the perceived usefulness of AI technologies (Abdelaal & Sawi, 2024; Kohnke et al., 2023). Theoretical frameworks such as the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) proposed by Davis (1989) and the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) model developed by Mishra & Koehler (2006) have been widely used to explain how educators adopt or resist new technologies. However, these models often focus on behavioural outcomes without sufficiently addressing how educators' professional identities, core beliefs, and teaching philosophies impact their decisions.

Although international research on AI in ELT is growing, relatively few studies focus specifically on Vietnamese university EFL lecturers. Much of the existing literature emphasises student use of AI (Ngo et al., 2024; Pham & Le, 2024) or theoretical speculation (Abdelaal & Sawi, 2024; Saliba, 2024), leaving a gap in understanding how teachers themselves experience and respond to AI in daily practice. Moreover, little research has examined the influence of personal teaching philosophies, institutional cultures, and ethical orientations on AI adoption in the Vietnamese context.

This study addresses that gap by qualitatively exploring Vietnamese EFL lecturers' responses to AI in language teaching. It seeks to understand not only their attitudes toward AI but also the underlying pedagogical and contextual factors that shape their engagement, whether that be acceptance, cautious use, or rejection.

The study addresses two key research questions:

1. What are Vietnamese university EFL lecturers' attitudes toward the use of AI in teaching?
2. What factors influence their acceptance or rejection of AI tools?

LITERATURE REVIEW

AI in English Language Teaching

The integration of AI in ELT has sparked growing academic interest, particularly with the emergence of tools like ChatGPT, Gemini and Copilot. These technologies can generate written texts, provide instant feedback, and support language interaction, creating pedagogical opportunities and ethical challenges (Pham & Le, 2024; Saliba, 2024).

Globally, educators have responded with a mix of enthusiasm and caution. On one hand, AI tools are seen as innovative aids that enhance creativity, diversify input, and support personalised learning (Aljabr & Al-Ahdal, 2024; Kohnke et al., 2023). On the other hand, there are concerns about over-reliance, increased plagiarism, and difficulty maintaining assessment integrity (Abdelaal & Sawi, 2024; Ngo et al., 2024). These tensions are shaping evolving practices in ELT classrooms.

Teacher Attitudes Toward AI in Education

Teacher attitudes toward AI range from strong resistance to open experimentation. Some studies highlight educators' fears that AI could undermine their professional roles or contribute to the dehumanisation of teaching (Abdelaal & Sawi, 2024). Saliba (2024) found that while some teachers welcomed AI's assistance, others were concerned about its impact on authentic student work and traditional pedagogy.

In the Vietnamese EFL context, Pham and Le (2024) reported a mix of curiosity and scepticism among university lecturers. While some acknowledged AI's potential to support learner engagement and creativity, others expressed concern about classroom control and fairness in assessment. Similarly, Ngo et al. (2024) found that many teachers viewed AI-assisted plagiarism as a growing threat to academic integrity, linked to students' lack of motivation or writing skills.

Factors Influencing AI Acceptance or Rejection

The TAM proposed by Davis (1989) provides a useful lens for understanding lecturers' decision-making regarding AI tools. TAM suggests that two factors shape technology adoption:

Perceived Usefulness – the extent to which technology enhances performance.

Perceived Ease of Use – how effortless the technology is to use.

Several studies have shown that when teachers view AI as practical and time-saving, they are more likely to integrate it into their teaching (Aljabr & Al-Ahdal, 2024). However, digital literacy, lack of training, and unclear institutional guidance often lead to cautious or negative attitudes (Kohnke et al., 2023). Ngo et al. (2024) further noted that time pressure and limited student skill development also push teachers to reconsider how and when to allow AI in their classrooms.

In addition to TAM, the TPACK framework (Mishra & Koehler, 2006) offers a complementary perspective by emphasising the importance of aligning technological tools with both pedagogical strategies and content knowledge. This study draws on both models to better understand how lecturers in Vietnamese tertiary education evaluate and implement AI in ways that reflect not only perceived usefulness and ease of use, but also their professional knowledge and instructional goals.

Teaching Philosophies and Identity in Technology Adoption

Beyond technical and institutional factors, teachers' beliefs and philosophies play a key role in shaping their engagement with educational technology. Research on teacher identity highlights how educators interpret and implement innovations through the lens of their personal values and pedagogical goals (Beijaard et al., 2004; Rodgers & Scott, 2008).

These identity constructs often mediate technology adoption, as shown in Ertmer's (1999) work, distinguishing between first-order (external) and second-order (belief-based) barriers. First-order barriers involve

logistical issues such as access, time, and resources, while second-order barriers stem from teachers' deep-seated beliefs about instruction and learning barriers, which Ertmer argues are often more resistant to change and require pedagogical, not just technical interventions.

For humanistic teachers, emotional connection, care, and relational presence may take precedence over efficiency or automation. These educators are often guided by care ethics and emphasise the moral and emotional dimensions of teaching (Noddings, 2012). In contrast, constructivist educators may view AI more positively, welcoming it as a tool to promote student-centred learning and scaffolded instruction, consistent with principles from Vygotsky's (1978) sociocultural theory, where mediated tools assist in cognitive development. This study draws on such frameworks to better understand how Vietnamese EFL lecturers position themselves regarding AI integration in the classroom.

Research Gap

Although international research on AI in ELT is expanding, relatively few studies focus on Vietnamese university EFL lecturers, especially from a teacher-centred and context-sensitive perspective. Much of the existing literature emphasises students' use of AI tools or discusses theoretical and ethical implications in general terms, often overlooking the lived experiences of educators who mediate AI's integration into the classroom.

Moreover, previous studies tend to focus on attitudes at the surface level (Abdelaal & Sawi, 2024; Kohnke et al., 2023; Saliba, 2024), without sufficiently examining how those attitudes are shaped by lecturers' teaching philosophies, institutional environments, and professional identities. This leaves a significant gap in understanding how and why teachers adopt, adapt to, or resist AI in their daily practice.

This study addresses that gap by qualitatively exploring how Vietnamese university EFL lecturers form attitudes toward AI and what personal, pedagogical, and institutional factors influence their decisions to accept, reject, or cautiously explore its use in teaching.

METHODS

Research Design

This study adopts a qualitative research approach to explore Vietnamese EFL lecturers' attitudes toward the use of AI in teaching. It aims to understand their perceptions and the key factors influencing their acceptance or rejection of AI tools. As an exploratory study, it aims to gain in-depth insights into how lecturers interpret, mediate, and respond to the integration of AI within their instructional practices.

Given the limited prior research on Vietnamese EFL lecturers' responses to AI, a qualitative design was particularly appropriate. Unlike surveys, which may constrain responses, semi-structured interviews enabled participants to elaborate on their personal experiences, reflect on ethical concerns, and express nuanced attitudes. This method offered a rich, contextualised understanding of the topic, grounded in the lecturers' lived realities and professional perspectives.

Participants

The participants in this study were Vietnamese university lecturers who teach EFL across a range of higher education institutions, including public universities, private institutions, and academies. A purposive sampling method was adopted to recruit individuals who had direct experience using AI tools in their teaching or had developed informed opinions regarding the pedagogical implications of AI integration.

A total of 17 lecturers were invited to participate in the study. All were identified through the researchers' professional and academic acquaintances and were contacted via social media platforms such as Facebook and Zalo. Each participant received a brief overview of the study, an official invitation, and a participant consent form.

Of these:

- 2 lecturers took part in a pilot phase, which was used to refine the interview protocol.
- 1 lecturer initially consented but did not respond to subsequent interview scheduling.
- 14 lecturers completed full interviews and formed the main participant sample used in the final analysis.

The 14 main participants included 11 females and 3 males, aged between 25 and 44 years ($M = 35.7$). Their teaching experience ranged from 0.5 to 20 years ($M = 8.2$), and they represented diverse institutions located in Hà Nội, Ninh Bình, Nghệ An, and Vĩnh Phúc. The lecturers taught various courses, including General English, English for Specific Purposes (ESP), and English Linguistics.

To be included in the study, participants needed to:

- Have prior experience with AI tools in their teaching (e.g., ChatGPT, Gemini, Grammarly, Copilot, Canva, iSpring), or
- Possess clear, informed views about the use of AI in EFL instruction.
- This sample reflects a wide range of institutional types, teaching contexts, and AI engagement levels, offering a rich foundation for exploring lecturers' responses to AI in language education.

Data Collection

Data for this study were collected through semi-structured interviews, which served as the sole data collection instrument. This method was chosen due to its flexibility in exploring complex, evolving phenomena like AI used in teaching. Semi-structured interviews allow for open-ended responses while maintaining consistency across participants, making them particularly effective for eliciting in-depth insights into individual beliefs, attitudes, and contextual influences (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

The final interview guide comprised 15 open-ended questions, structured around three key thematic areas:

- General attitudes toward AI in English language teaching
- Perceived benefits, challenges, and concerns related to AI integration
- Influencing factors, including technological access, institutional support, training, and ethical implications

The 15 interview questions were developed based on a thorough review of the literature. Studies by Abdelaal and Sawi (2024) and Saliba (2024) informed questions on general perceptions. The TAM (Davis, 1989) guided questions on perceived usefulness and ease of use. The TPACK framework (Mishra & Koehler, 2006) also informed question design by highlighting the importance of aligning AI tools with lecturers' subject knowledge and teaching practices. Questions related to institutional and training-related challenges were drawn from Kohnke et al. (2023) and Pham and Le (2024). Ethical issues were grounded in Aljabr and Al-Ahdal (2024), while pedagogical concerns were adapted from Saliba (2024). This interview design ensured that both theoretical constructs and practical realities were captured in a way that honoured participant voice and contextual specificity.

Two pilot interviews were conducted to test the clarity, flow, and relevance of the questions. Minor refinements were made to improve the wording and sequencing based on pilot feedback.

All interviews were conducted via Zoom video calls and lasted approximately 15 to 30 minutes each. To ensure participant comfort and authentic expression, interviews were conducted in Vietnamese. Participants were recruited through the researchers' professional networks and contacted via Facebook and Zalo, where they received an overview of the study, an invitation, and a consent form.

Data Analysis

Data were analysed using Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase thematic analysis framework, selected for its suitability in identifying patterns within qualitative data. The aim was to explore EFL lecturers' attitudes toward AI and the contextual factors shaping those views.

All interviews were video-recorded (with consent), transcribed via TurboScribe.ai, and manually checked for accuracy. Transcripts were analysed in Vietnamese to preserve nuance, with selected excerpts later translated into English.

Coding was conducted using Taguette, beginning with a deductive framework based on the literature review, such as acceptance, caution, rejection, ethical concerns, and institutional factors. As analysis progressed, inductive codes also emerged, capturing metaphors (e.g., “fast food”), emotional tensions, and evolving perceptions over time.

The six steps of Braun and Clarke’s (2006) thematic analysis were followed:

1. Familiarising with the data by repeated reading of transcripts
2. Generating initial codes to capture the semantic and latent meaning
3. Searching for themes by clustering related codes
4. Reviewing themes to ensure internal consistency and relevance
5. Defining and naming themes to refine the story told by the data
6. Producing the report by selecting vivid, representative quotes for each theme

The themes were then mapped onto the study’s two research questions:

1. What are Vietnamese university EFL lecturers’ attitudes toward the use of AI in teaching?
2. What factors influence their acceptance or rejection of AI tools?

The initial thematic findings identified six overarching themes: *Attitudes towards AI* (ranging from rejection to acceptance), *Benefits and Opportunities* (perceived time-saving and efficiency), *Challenges and Ethical Concerns* (student overreliance; source inaccuracy; critical thinking erosion), *Influencing Factors* (institutional policy support; lack of AI training; ethical concerns), *Human Role and Future Outlook* (human role emphasised; future integration optimism; desire for pedagogical guidelines), and *Influence of Personal Teaching Philosophies* (AI as Assistant, not replacement; ethical guidance as part of teaching responsibility). Each theme is supported by rich, bilingual quotes to convey the depth and diversity of the lecturers’ perspectives.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Building on the above-mentioned thematic insights, this section presents detailed findings from interviews with 14 Vietnamese university EFL lecturers. Thematic analysis identified core patterns related to lecturer attitudes, perceived benefits and challenges of AI, institutional influences, evolving teacher roles, future outlooks, and personal teaching philosophies. Table 1 summarises how frequently these themes appeared and provides illustrative responses that highlight both shared and individual perspectives.

Table 1. Summary of Key Themes, Frequency of Mentions, and Illustrative Lecturer Responses

Theme	Lecturers mentioned (n = 14)	Typical Response (VN → EN)
Acceptance	13	“Mình thấy nó tích cực. Và mình cũng xác định là mình dùng, thì sinh viên cũng sẽ dùng. Thậm chí là các bạn ấy còn nhanh nhẹn hơn cả mình.” → I see AI as something positive. I also realise that if I use it, my students will use it too. They are even quicker with it than I am. (Lecturer 5)
Caution	12	“Cần kiểm tra lại nội dung vì AI đôi khi sai.” → AI's content needs verification as it can be wrong. (Lecturer 14)
Rejection	5	“AI chỉ là công cụ hỗ trợ, không thể thay thế con người.” → AI is merely a support tool; it cannot replace people. (Lecturer 11)
Time-saving	12	“Tiết kiệm rất nhiều thời gian so với trước kia.” → It saves a lot of time compared to before. (Lecturer 8)
Enhanced Productivity and Lesson Planning Support	10	“AI hỗ trợ giáo viên trong việc thiết kế bài giảng, tài liệu, handout trên lớp. Nhờ AI, các công việc này được hoàn thành nhanh chóng hơn, tiết kiệm thời gian và sức lực cho giáo viên.” → It assists in designing lesson plans, materials, and handouts for class. Thanks to AI, these tasks are completed faster, saving teachers both time and effort. (Lecturer 9)
Student Overreliance	11	“Sinh viên chỉ copy từ AI mà không hiểu gì.” → Students just copy from AI without understanding. (Lecturer 6)
Source Inaccuracy	9	“Trích dẫn từ AI nhiều khi không tìm thấy nguồn. Mình kiểm chứng lại thì không có cái nguồn ở trên web.” → AI citations are often untraceable. I verified the information and couldn't find a source. (Lecturer 14)
Critical Thinking Erosion	10	“Học qua AI giống như ăn fast food, dễ tiếp cận nhưng nông.” → Learning through AI is like fast food, which is accessible but shallow. (Lecturer 1)
Human Role Emphasised	10	“Giáo viên có cảm xúc, còn AI thì không.” → Teachers have emotions; AI doesn't. (Lecturer 13)
Institutional Policy Support	9	“Trường tổ chức workshop, cấp tài khoản miễn phí.” → The university gave workshops and free AI accounts. (Lecturer 12)
Lack of AI Training	8	“Chưa từng được đào tạo bài bản về AI.” → I've never received formal training on AI. (Lecturer 13)
Ethical Concerns	10	“Em rất quan ngại về phẩm chất chung của con người, chứ không chỉ riêng nhà giáo. Đó là tính trung thực và việc đề cao giá trị trong sạch của bản thân.” → I am very concerned about the overall human quality, not just teachers, particularly honesty and the upholding of personal integrity. (Lecturer 3)
Future Integration Optimism	11	“Tôi nghĩ AI sẽ là một phần tất yếu trong tương lai.” → I think AI will inevitably be part of the future. (Lecturer 14)
AI as Assistant, not Replacement	13	“AI chỉ là công cụ hỗ trợ...” → AI is a support tool, not a replacement for humans. (Lecturer 6)
Ethical Guidance as Part of Teaching Responsibility	4	“Bên cạnh việc dạy kiến thức, mình nghĩ việc hướng dẫn sinh viên sử dụng AI một cách đúng đắn và có đạo đức cũng quan trọng không kém.” → Besides teaching content, I believe that guiding students to use AI correctly and ethically is equally important. (Lecturer 10)
Desire for Pedagogical Guidelines	9	“Nên có quy định rõ ràng về cách dùng AI trong giảng dạy.” → There should be clear rules on how to use AI in teaching. (Lecturer 10)

Interpretation of Findings

The findings reveal a nuanced and multidimensional landscape of how Vietnamese EFL lecturers respond to integrating AI in their teaching practices. While the overall tone is cautiously optimistic, attitudes are shaped by lecturers' pedagogical philosophies, teaching contexts, technological literacy, and institutional environments. This section elaborates on key patterns and socio-institutional tensions, with each major theme encompassing several focused subthemes.

Acceptance as Pragmatic Embrace, Not Blind Adoption

Among the 14 participants, 13 expressed positive views toward AI integration, particularly for administrative and preparatory tasks. As indicated by Lecturer 5 (Table 1), many saw AI as practical support, acknowledging its usefulness and students' even greater adaptability.

However, acceptance was rarely unconditional. Some, such as Lecturer 9, highlighted AI's time-saving benefits in lesson planning and material preparation, while Lecturer 13 described using ChatGPT to streamline

assessment design. Importantly, this pragmatic embrace was shaped within clear professional boundaries. As Lecturers 6 and 11 noted, most lecturers positioned AI as an instructional assistant, not a replacement for human educators, thus safeguarding their pedagogical identities and roles.

While perceived usefulness was a key motivator, as conceptualised in Davis's (1989) TAM, lecturers' decisions also reflected how well AI aligned with their instructional methods and subject matter. This resonates with the TPACK framework (Mishra & Koehler, 2006), which emphasises the integration of technological, pedagogical and content knowledge. Lecturers appeared most confident and open to AI when its use complemented, not conflicted with, their teaching strategies and content delivery.

Caution and Ethical Vigilance

Despite broad acceptance, caution was present. 12 lecturers raised concerns about the reliability of AI-generated content. As summarised in Table 1, Lecturer 14 and others reported instances where AI citations were fabricated or unverifiable, echoing Aljabr and Al-Ahdal's (2024) warnings about epistemic instability in AI systems.

Rather than reflecting resistance to technology, this caution represented ethical vigilance, a professional commitment to protecting students from shallow engagement, misinformation, overreliance or unverified content.

Student Overreliance and the Erosion of Critical Thinking

A primary concern, stated by 11 participants, was that AI use could undermine students' critical thinking skills. Lecture 6, for example, observed that students often copied AI outputs without understanding.

Lecturer 1 metaphorically compared AI-driven learning to consuming fast food, easily accessible but lacking intellectual nourishment.

A major concern, voiced by 11 participants, was that AI use could undermine students' critical thinking skills. Lecturer 6, for example, observed that students often copied AI outputs without understanding. This metaphor formed broader fears that AI may facilitate superficial productivity without deep cognitive engagement, a concern similarly noted by Ngo et al. (2024).

In response, some lecturers, such as Lecturer 14, adjusted their assessment strategies, requiring in-class handwritten work to mitigate dependency on AI.

Role of the Teacher: Irreplaceable Yet Repositioned

Despite recognising AI's capabilities, 10 lecturers strongly asserted the irreplaceability of human teachers. As Table 1 shows, Lecturer 13 emphasised the emotional dimension of teaching, highlighting that AI lacks human empathy, intuition, and ethical guidance.

Rather than perceiving AI as a threat, the lecturers envisioned a repositioned role, moving from knowledge deliverers to facilitators of judgement, creativity and ethical reasoning. This aligns with Saliba's (2024) view that AI should promote, not replace, the humanistic core of education.

Institutional Influence and Gaps

Institutional landscapes play a crucial role in shaping lecturers' AI engagement. Some participants, like Lecturer 12, benefited from university-organised workshops and free AI account access. Nonetheless, many others, including Lecturer 13, reported receiving no formal training, resulting in inconsistent and inequitable practices.

This institutional divide underscores the importance of clear policy frameworks and structured professional development to ensure responsible and equitable AI integration across institutions.

Looking Ahead: Hope and Hesitation

Despite their reservations, most lecturers expressed optimism about AI's future role in education. Lecturer 14 articulated a widespread belief that AI will inevitably become integral to teaching.

Lecturers, however, emphasised the necessity of ethical guardrails and pedagogical guidelines. As stressed

by Lecturer 10, clear institutional rules are essential to guide ethical and effective AI use. This enthusiasm is constrained by responsible integration, driven by transparency, accountability, and educational purpose.

Influence of Personal Teaching Philosophies

Beyond technological and institutional factors, lecturers' responses to AI were deep-seated in their teaching philosophies:

Humanistic educators (e.g., Lecturers 10 and 13) emphasised emotional connection, ethical responsibility, relational trust, and a renewed commitment to guiding students how to ethically use AI, perceiving it with scepticism for its lack of empathetic dimensions. Their perspectives align with Noddings' (2012) ethics of care, which foregrounds the relational and moral foundations of teaching.

Constructivist educators, like Lecturer 5, were more open to AI as a scaffold for learner-centred activities, echoing with Vygotsky's (1978) sociocultural theory, where tools mediate development when guided critically. This also aligns with the TPACK framework (Mishra & Koehler, 2006), as these lecturers effectively integrated AI with both pedagogical intentions and content objectives.

Technologically hesitant educators, including Lecturers 1 and 3, raised concerns about AI's influence on academic integrity, critical thinking and core human values. Lecturer 3's emphasis on honesty and personal integrity underlines that their hesitation was principled, not merely based on technological unfamiliarity.

These patterns reinforce Ertmer's (1999) concept of second-order barriers, deeply held pedagogical beliefs affecting technology adoption, and resonate with Rodgers and Scott's (2008) model of teacher identity evolution in response to contextual shifts.

The findings reveal that Vietnamese EFL lecturers' responses to AI are diverse and shaped by personal beliefs, institutional contexts, and ethical concerns. Rather than a simple accept-or-reject stance, their attitudes reflect an ongoing negotiation between innovation, caution, and professional identity. These insights suggest important implications for policy, training, and future research.

Implications

The findings highlight key implications for EFL teaching, teacher training, and institutional policy in Vietnam and beyond. AI integration should be belief-sensitive and ethically grounded, addressing not just technical skills but also pedagogy and teacher identity. Universities must provide structured support, including professional development, ethical guidelines, and resources, to ensure responsible use without compromising academic integrity. AI tools should be perceived as instructional assistants within human-centred pedagogies, not replacements. Finally, policy initiatives must respect lecturers' professional beliefs and classroom realities, avoiding top-down mandates based purely on technological trends.

Limitations

The first limitation is the relatively small and context-specific sample size (14 Vietnamese EFL lecturers), which may limit the generalisability of findings. The reliance on self-reported interviews may not fully reflect actual classroom practices or changing perceptions over time. Additionally, as the study was conducted during a period of rapid AI development, participants' views may evolve with new technologies and policies. Finally, the focus on lecturers leaves students' perspectives, administrative policies and cross-institutional comparisons for future research.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

This study explored how Vietnamese university EFL lecturers respond to the integration of AI in English language teaching. Based on qualitative data from 14 interviews, the findings reveal a spectrum of attitudes, from enthusiastic acceptance to cautious engagement and partial rejection, shaped by pedagogical, ethical, institutional, and personal factors.

While most lecturers recognised AI's practical benefits, particularly for time-saving and lesson preparation, many expressed concerns about student overreliance, critical thinking erosion, and content reliability, leading to selective adoption practices.

Lecturers' responses were mediated not only by external factors but also by deep-seated teaching philosophies. Humanistic educators emphasised care, emotional presence, moral responsibility, and a renewed commitment to guiding students to use AI ethically. Constructivist educators embraced AI as a scaffold for learning, while traditionally minded lecturers stressed academic rigour and personal integrity.

The findings highlight that AI adoption is interpreted through the lens of teaching philosophies, reflecting broader questions about the kind of education lecturers seek to foster.

Recommendations

Based on these findings, the following practical and policy-level recommendations are proposed:

Institutional Policy and Support:

Provide clear, context-sensitive guidelines for AI use; respect teaching autonomy rather than enforcing uniform adoption.

Training and Professional Development:

Expand AI training beyond technical skills to include pedagogy, assessment redesign, and ethical reasoning.

Curriculum and Assessment Reform:

Design tasks that emphasise originality, reflection, and process; co-develop AI-aware assessment policies with teachers.

Promote Teacher Agency and Dialogue:

Create spaces for ongoing dialogue; support belief-informed innovation, respecting diverse teaching identities.

Future Research Directions:

Conduct longitudinal studies to examine how lecturers' attitudes evolve over time with exposure and training;
Compare responses across regions, disciplines, and institutional types;
Include student perspectives on the ethical, creative, and learning dimensions of AI use in EFL contexts.

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